

THE ROLE OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN THE TEACHING OF RAILWAY SPECIALISTS

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Annotation: *The article discusses the importance of English language in exchange training. There are various levels of ownership of a foreign language: basic, implying knowledge of grammar and lexical minimal, technical (professional dictionary) or conversation. For some, learning foreign languages is an exciting hobby for others - an integral part of the work.*

Keywords: *foreign language, English, railway specialists, education, language skills*

The relevance of this topic is determined by the fact that the process of globalization, namely the process of global political, cultural, economic integration. The formation of the only world market economy, the creation of a common information space and, therefore, the number of contacts between people from different countries increases. In this regard, the need for specialists who know a foreign language is only increasing. Many universities and schools conduct exchange training. Young people participate in international sports competitions and Olympiads, where students begin new acquaintances with foreigners, experience in the exchange and recognition of culture, customs of each other.

English is a working and official language of the UN. Each world act, technical publication, book, training, song, poster, letter will be read and understood by different nations and peoples if they are represented in English.

Turks and Finns, Czechs and Hungarians, Italians, Russians and Uzbeks, not knowing each other's language, will be able to communicate with each other in this language. More than 450 million people consider this a family. Another 600-650 million citizens use English as an additional language for communication. This is considered in demand in many countries of the world. Knowledge of the vocabulary and grammar of this language is extremely necessary for undergoing training abroad. You cannot do without it and wanting to find a prestigious and highly paid job. [2]

In all countries of the world, the study of English is very important. Almost everyone wants to study this, at least at the initial level. Today children are starting to study the language in preschool age. Many do not understand whether English is needed in the modern world. Nevertheless, it is no secret to anyone that today it plays an important role when applying for a job. People who want to find a prestigious and

highly paid position should not know English well. This is due to the fact that large companies often cooperate with foreign partners. To date, English is an international language. They should be pretty good to fully agree and conclude transactions with foreign partners.

Requirements for a future specialist, living conditions in modern society, make demands on finding new approaches to the preparation of just such a specialist.

Today, a conversation in a foreign language is the need and distinctive personality quality. The revolution in the scientific and technical fields follow the information explosion, all this brought us the absence and participation of specialists in international scientific and technical relations, as well as the integration of cultural and business contacts. [1]

Education at the university should be considered as an obligatory discipline of specialists in training with higher education. The concept of modern education in the secondary higher educational institution includes a specialized learning system plus language skills, which provides a small adaptation to the dynamics of changes in the conditions of professional activity. Many students devote more and more time to studying not only English, but also at least one or two foreign languages. You can meet a combination of English, Spanish, German and Chinese. Students with knowledge of the language are interesting to improve the language and expand knowledge about the country's culture. Employers are interested in the presence of specialists who speak this language as their employees, regardless of the intensity of its use. The exception is rare professionals with extensive experience, but there will still be the perfect candidate who knows the language. The degree of knowledge of the language serves as an indicator of the level of human education and its prospects for the company. [3]

Over the past two decades, in training specialists, a lot of attention has been paid to project activities that are accustomed to creative thinking in order to independently plan their actions, predict possible solutions to the tasks that he faces, implementing the means of work and methods of work. In the process of preparing the project, students of different countries can communicate in foreign languages. For a conductor, foreign languages play a big role as the conductor serves passengers along the train route and ensures their safety. If these international paths, he should additionally know: a foreign language in the amount provided for by a special training program to maintain international messages necessary for communication with passengers on official issues. Conductors and stewardesses spend almost all their lives on business trips. These professions allow not only every day to communicate with different people and become the face of their company, but also to visit many cities in and abroad for free. English is an international language of communication, every educated person must know it, at least at the basic level.

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